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“MEDICATED CIGARETTES: A PROMISING UNUSUAL DOSAGE FORM”

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ABSTRACT

Several route of administration of drug have not only been described but also practiced for numerous times. Depending upon the physical property of drug it can be injected, swallowed, applied, instilled etc by selecting suitable dosage form for the administration. Similarly the medicines can be administered through smoke by the use of medicated cigarettes. Convenience of administration and patient compliance are gaining significant importance in the design of dosage forms. Recently, more emphasis is laid down on the development of an organoleptically elegant and patient-friendly drug delivery system for patients. Novelty in terms of dosage form designing is needed for several reasons like taste masking, better therapeutic efficacy etc but the primary objective is better patient compliance. Unusual dosage form compared to routine / conventional dosage forms are better in terms of its user friendly nature. So, better patient compliance can be achieved. We hesitate to talk about “Cigarette”, but this technique could be used for delivery of medicine; it could be interesting to study and apply for research.! The concept of medicated cigarette is discussed in detail with emphasis on history, development and future scope in this field.

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INTRODUCTION

Medicated Cigarette: [1, 2]

Are cigarettes that usually composed of mixture medicinally active materials that may have tobacco or may be tobacco free! The medicament is filled inside in a wrap. It is sucked in by mouth or by nose, but exhaled by mouth, since exhalation when done by nose may irritate eyes.

In old days several common and uncommon illness was regularly treated through way of smoke inhalation of various herbs, treatments like Acute sinusitis, Asthma, Lungs Cleaning, Internal Healings, Insomnia, Tension, Sneezing, Infections of the Upper and lower respiratory tract, Common Cough and cold, Rhinitis, Mind Relaxation, Nasal polyps, Common and acute Head ache, various ulcers, skin problems etc.

At the end of the smoking duration, there may be some signs of the process for completion of the smoking.

It might be:

- Melting of phlegm.
- Cleanness in the air passage.
- Relief from discomfort.

Origin: [3]

Dhumapanam (Medical Smoking) is a concept from Ayurveda that is prescribed as a medication in the history of Ayurveda. Ayurveda has mentioned that after performing kaval and Gandusha one should perform Dhumapanam (medical smoking) and application of aromatic and soothing herbs like kasturi and chandan etc. by performing Dhumapanam, udharv jatru gata roga (above neck organs including trachea) gets disease free from vata and kapha disorders.

According to usage it is classified into four types

1. Prayogika
2. Vairechanika
3. Snehika
4. Kasaghna

Prayogika smoking is of moderate intensity and is advised for regular use by persons of kapha prakruti (constitution), rest three are used in diseases for which physician has to be consulted.

Preparation of medicated cigarette:

A grass stick of about 3 to 12 anguli (finger units) is selected and kept immersed in water for about 24hours, ones should use ones middle finger for measuring the stick.

Then it is coated 5 times with the thick paste prepared after examining the person and his prakruti and herbs are chosen accordingly. It is to be remembered that the second coat is to be applied only after the first has dried. The stick is then coated to assure the girth of one's toe in the center and ends are tapered. After all this when it becomes dried, the grass stick should be removed. Now this supposedly cigarette is coated with ghee and is dried in shade. This is placed in a pipe for smoking.

The smoking tube or pipe should be strait and made up of metal or wood or bamboo. It consists of three parts with an opening that would admit ones toe or thumb at the broader end and ones smallest finger at the narrower end.

Methods of smoking:

A person should sit strait, keep his mouth open and start drawing in the smoke through the nostril alternately, three times through each nostril, if the disease or doshas are in the head or nose e.g. sinusitis. For diseases of the throat, pharynx, larynx and lower respiratory tract, the smoke should be drawn through mouth. The smoke should be exhaled through the mouth and not through the nose because this can irritate the eyes.

Timings of smoking:

Dhumapanam can be done after bath, after lunch or dinner, after brushing the teeth, after applying Anjanam (collyrium) to eyes or just after getting from bed in morning.

Contraindications:

- People below 18 years.
- Pregnant ladies.
- People with head injuries.
- People with eye diseases like timir (cataract).
- Pandu (anemia) and bleeding tendencies.
- After excessive virechan (purgation) and enema.
- Moorcha (fainting), trishna (excessive thirst and dryness of throat).
- Person who is injured.
- After excessive work and overexertion.
- People who are emotionally disturbed.
- Person who has consumed fish, Madd (alcohol), or any poisonous substance.

Effect of Dhumapanam on body:

- It prevents vata and kapha disorder of nose, mouth, throat, and air passage situated above the clavicle.
- It exerts its tonic effect on larynx, sense organs and sinuses.
- It prevents premature graying and falling of hairs.
- It is very effective in excessive salivation, itching in the mouth, cold, sneezing, sinusitis, halitosis, pain in the ear, discharge from the nose, ears and eyes, weakness of teeth, toothache, enlargement of tonsils and uvula, stiffness of jaw and neck, cough, breathlessness, hiccups, drowsiness, excessive sleep.
- It exerts soothing action on the sense organs, speech and the mind

Signs of adequate smoking:

- Feeling of cleanliness in the nose, ears, throat, air passage and heart.
- Feeling of lightness on head, throat and chest.
- Melting of sticky phlegm.

Signs of excessive smoking:

- Hyper stimulation of sensory and motor organs, mouth and throat become warm and dry.
- The person becomes giddy, confused, drowsy, thirst and develops abdominal distension
- Hoarseness of voice, hyperacidity, tinnitus, deafness and bleeding disorders are common.
- Increase chest damages the mucous membrane resulting in the lowered resistance to infection, which vitiates vata and kapha doshas.

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT:**Ayurveda:** [4, 5]

The history of smoking dates back to as early as 5000 BCE in shamanistic rituals. Many ancient civilizations such as the Babylonians, Indians and Chinese burnt incense as a part of religious rituals, as did the Israelites and the later Catholic and Orthodox Christian churches. Smoking in the Americas probably had its origins in the incense-burning ceremonies of shamans but was later adopted for pleasure, or as a social tool. The smoking of tobacco, as well as various hallucinogenic drugs, was used to achieve trances and to come into contact with the spirit world.

Cannabis smoking in India has been known since at least 2000 BC and is first mentioned in the Atharvaveda, which dates back a few hundred years BC. Fumigation (dhupa) and fire offerings (homa) are prescribed in the Ayurveda for medical purposes and have been practiced for at least 3,000 years while smoking, dhumrapana (literally "drinking smoke"), has been practiced for at least 2,000 years.

Before modern times, smoking was done with pipes with stems of various lengths, or chillums. Today dhumapana has been replaced almost entirely by cigarette smoking, but both dhupa and homa are still practiced.

Beedi, a type of hand rolled herbal cigarette consisting of cloves, ground betel nut, and tobacco, usually with rather low proportion of tobacco, are a modern descendant of the historical dhumapana.

In 1560: [6]

A Frenchman named Jean Nicot (from whose name the word nicotine derives) introduced tobacco to France in 1560 from Spain. From there, it spread to England. The first report of a smoking Englishman is of a sailor in Bristol in 1556, seen "emitting smoke from his nostrils." Like tea, coffee and opium, tobacco was just one of many intoxicants originally used as a form of medicine.

In 19th century: [7]

Nineteenth-century opinion on the subject of smoking was sharply divided. On the one hand there were many prominent doctors who condemned the practice as unhealthy, and even suggested that it caused cancers of the mouth; on the other, there were plenty of physicians who believed that smoking eased coughs and other respiratory disorders by promoting the production of mucus.

In 1851: [7]

In 1851 the London Medical Journal came out strongly in favour of smoking as a means of taking medicine.

J. H. Richards, of Philadelphia, writes as follows in the Medical Examiner for June 1851 – “I have been informed by a gentleman of intelligence, who has resided for a long time in China and Manilla, that mercury, which is their regarded as a specific in the severe forms of hepatic disorder incident to the climate and is constantly exhibited in the following novel and peculiar manner. The black oxide is introduced into the Manilla cheroots, and, being inhaled, is thus presented in the form of vapour to the most absorbent surface in the body. I mention this fact, as it is interesting in itself, and may suggest other applications of the same principle.”

In 1863: [7]

The Canada Lancet gave a list of recipes for other ‘medicinal’ cigarettes.

Arsenical Cigarettes.

Nitre Cigarettes.—Dip the paper in a saturated solution of the nitrate of potash before rolling. Nitrate of potash, also known as saltpetre, is potassium nitrate, a component of gunpowder. Smoke with due caution. Balsamic Cigarettes are made by giving the dried nitre cigarettes a coating of tincture of benzoin. Tincture of benzoin is still sometimes inhaled in steam today, to ease the symptoms of bronchitis.

The article concludes with a list of some of the miraculous cures attributed to medicated cigarettes:

Aphonia:

A patient who could not speak above a whisper for over a year, probably due to a thickened condition of the chordae vocales, as she had no pain or constitutional symptoms, used the mercurial cigarettes for a month, and perfectly recovered.

Offensive Discharges from the Nostrils, with a sense of uneasiness in the frontal sinuses, was quite cured in about a month with the mercurial cigarettes. The patient held his nose after taking a mouthful of the smoke, and then forced it into his nostrils in the manner practised by accomplished smokers.

Polypus in the Nose:

A patient, who had been twice operated upon for polypus, is now able to keep the disposition to form fresh polypi in check, by smoking the mercurial cigarette in the same manner, when he feels that uneasiness which warns him of the danger of its recurrence.

Phthisis:

Trousseau long ago recommended a puff or two of an arsenical cigarette twice or three times a day in phthisis.

Finally, the Canada Medical Journal for 1863 has an alternative for heavier smokers – sometimes a mere cigarette doesn't quite hit the spot:

Mr. Davis of this city has prepared medicated cigars with a view of affording to those who are smokers a means of indulging in the weed, at the same time that they can by the same means procure medication. Smoking stramonium, conium, belladonna and other narcotics is no novelty.

All were, however, commonly used in 19th-century medicine in one form or another.

And we find in works on the subject of materia medica mention made of this method of introducing these agents into the system. Those who prefer smoking to swallowing drugs, have thus an opportunity afforded them of indulging their appetite. Each box contains ten cigars, which are well made, and full particulars are given as to the method of using them. They are to be had of all druggists.

When the attention of the profession has been duly aroused to this subject, there will doubtless be found much other affection in which medicated cigarettes may be advantageously employed.

Work done in this field:**A) Patent US2418296: [8]**

Medicated Cigarette Filed April 17, 1944,

This invention relates to medicated tobacco, and more particularly to a medicated cigarette useful in 'the relief of the symptoms of hay fever.

Figure 1 is a perspective view of a medicated cigarette embodying the principles of the invention;

Figure 2 shows more or less diagrammatically, a group of tobacco flakes, showing in mixture, certain flakes medicated and others unmediated, in a ratio contemplated by the invention.

Cigarette useful in the relief of hay fever comprising a mixture of a major portion of untreated tobacco flakes and a minor portion of tobacco flakes coated, to the substantial exclusion of absorption, with a substance, in solid state, selected from the following group: mutton tallow, lanolin.

B) Chinese Patent CN 1297768 A: [9]

Medicated cigarette for treating pulmonary tuberculosis and its making process:

The present invention has fast and high curative effect and no toxic side effect. . Smoking the medicated cigarette can treat pulmonary tuberculosis.

Astragalus membranaceus, turtle shell, fritillary, Rhizoma bletillae, Cordyceps and other Chinese medicinal materials are prepared into cigarette through a special process.

The components were manufactured cost production methods of the invention is to smoke the drug:

- 1) The thirty-seven crushed to 100 mesh powder;
- 2) Astragalus, turtle, fritillary, Baiji, Cordyceps, Gecko, angelica root, skullcap, North almonds crushed to 120 mesh powder;
- 3) The gelatin in water After frying the resulting powder was added after 2 Stir in dried at a temperature of 15-20 ° C diarrhea Yang;
- 4) Resulting in the three conditions under 100-150 ° C aging, sterilized 30 minutes, made into 20 mesh powder particles;
- 5) The four resulting powder particles are mixed into each cigarette smoke the drug in tobacco-containing drugs in 5-6g.

An important feature of the present invention is easy to smoke the drug is administered, the patient simply smoke inhalation every two to 10 days for a course of treatment, usually 1-2 treatments that can achieve clinical cure.

C) Mexican Patent: [10]

Medicated cigarette for preventing myocardial infarction

Patent No- MXNL03000004 of Mexico (Fernando Rofee Samaniego):

This invention demonstrates that placing 10mg of aspirin in each cigarette it is reduced the platelet aggregation, enough as to not forming the haemostatic plug avoiding myocardial infarction or cerebral infarction thus preventing thousands of deaths each year, with a well-tolerated aspirin dose of between 75 and 325 mg, daily in a consumption of 10 to 50 cigarettes per day enough quantity as to block cyclooxygenase and not producing haemorrhages.

Medicated / Herbal cigarettes in different countries: [11]

China:

The Chinese Tobacco industry markets herbal cigarettes as having health benefits, yet scientific studies show there is no difference to peoples' health between Chinese herbal cigarette brands and regular cigarette brands.

Chinese cigarette brands are equally as addictive as regular cigarettes, although they are marketed as healthier.

Chinese herbal cigarettes are sold in Philippines, Singapore, Indonesia, Malaysia, Cambodia, Myanmar, Canada, and Taiwan.

People observed in a study showed they smoked more herbal cigarettes than regular cigarettes.

Herbal cigarettes started in the 1970s and became popular in the 1990s.

Two of the biggest herbal brands in China, Jinsheng and Wuyeshen, sold 1%, or 20 billion cigarettes, of all cigarettes sold in China in 2008.

Korea:

In Korea regular cigarette prices have raised making herbal cigarettes a more popular smoking alternative.

Evidence shows people in Korea choose to use herbal cigarettes as a smoking cessation aid.

Sales of herbal cigarettes increased by 118% in 2014.

United States:

A study investigating smokers' perception on cigarette products thought of as "less harmful" than regular cigarettes found 3.3 % named herbal cigarettes, which was higher than medical nicotine at 2.4%.

Marketed Preparation:**A) Honeyrose: [12]**

Honeyrose Products, based in England, has been the market leader in production of tobacco free and nicotine free herbal cigarettes.

Established in 1910, Honeyrose Herbal Products, has been producing and perfecting its herbal cigarettes since 1960's.

For years, Company's mission has been to offer smokers a tobacco free alternative to regular cigarettes.

The result is an herbal cigarette which features 100% organic, wild crafted herbs such as clover leaves, marshmallow leaves and rose petals, which are matured in honey and fruit juices.

Honeyrose herbal cigarettes accommodate every taste and are available in the following flavors: Clove, Vanilla, Menthol, Strawberry, DeLuxe, and Blue & White.

It was also offering herbal cigars which have 100% herbal filler and tobacco leaf wrapper to accentuate the cigar look and feel.

Fig 3: Honey rosé cigarettes.

B) Black swan: [13]

It is developed in 2002 as a smoking choice Pure Herbal "Non Tobacco substitute"

Herbal Smoke is a unique mixture of Pure Himalayan and Indian herbs, blending is based on two Herbal Ancient Health and Healing sciences Called "Unani and Ayurveda".

"Black Swan" is "Enigma" of unique smoking pleasure of "999" different aromas, try "Just-ONE" to pick up your "Passion" and experience a unique smoking "Temptation" that's what all about "Black Swan" Pure Herbal Smoke !

It may also help in quit smoking.

In old days many common and uncommon illness was regularly treated through the way of smoke inhalation of various herbs, treatments like acute sinusitis, Asthma, Lung cleaning insomnia, Sneezing, Infections of the Upper and Lower respiratory tract, Common cough and cold, various ulcers and skin problems ,etc.

Fig 4: Black Swan cigarettes.

C) Nirdosh Cigarettes: [14]

It started its way on March, 1997, with basic objective is to bring this age-old medicine to each individual wherever they are in the world, so that they can get rid of their illnesses and sufferings and benefit from it. The total +2500 National and International Satisfied Clients.

It helps in quit smoking.

It contains herbs which help to stop smoking by natural.

It effective quit smoking remedies to stop cigarettes.

Contents: Basil, Clove, Liquorice, Turmeric, Gangal, Tendu leaf, Indian Cinnamon, Bishops Weed, Indian Bedellium.

To quit tobacco and Nicotine Smoking, Nirdosh Cigar can be used with the four basic tastes and it's good for the health also.

Fig 5: Nirdosh Cigar.

Health effects: [15, 16]**A) Benefits:**

- It relieves many ailments.
- Heaviness of the head, headache, rhinitis, pain in the eye, cough, obstruction in the throat, etc.
- It is healthy alternative to regular smoking.
- It prevents premature graying and falling of hairs.
- Your blood pressure and pulse return to normal and also Oxygen levels return to normal.
- It exerts soothing action on the sense organs, speech and the mind

B) Side effects:

- Research shows that herbal cigarettes compared with regular cigarettes can be just as harmful in terms of the carcinogens they carry.
- Dr. John Moore-Gillan, chairman of the British Lung Foundation, states the addictive qualities to herbal/medicated cigarettes may be taken out, however other harmful elements remain.
- A study on Chinese herbal cigarettes found they had about the same amount of carcinogens as regular cigarettes.
- There are toxic components of the smoke of herbal cigarettes which are similar to regular cigarettes.
- Aminobiphenyl can cause bladder cancer. CO can be fatal in "low concentration of approximately 667 µg/mL."
- CO can cause coronary artery disease as well.
- Short term symptoms of CO include headaches, dizziness, irritability and difficulty breathing.

Future Scope:

- ✓ Medicated cigarette concept could be used for any unexplored drugs/therapies-
- ✓ As cited by Charaka "The Nose is the Gateway to the head", so using this concept we can target nose and head for local and systemic therapies of the diseases of that particular region.
- ✓ Medicated cigarette needs heat and formation of smoke, which is inhaled; hence drugs which can withstand temperature change can be explored for this delivery system.
- ✓ Likewise cigarettes containing tobacco, medicinal cigarettes also have limitations of delivering carbon monoxide and other harmful agents while inhaling, so research could be directed to minimize or avoid such harmful agents.
- ✓ Modern medicated cigarettes have wrappings of thin paper while ancient systems have wrappings of natural origin like leaves, etc.
- ✓ So study of effect of such component on delivery system will also be interesting.
- ✓ Overall, medicinal cigarette concept gives a wide scope for unexplored areas in modern system of medicine to make it an effective and patient friendly dosage form.

CONCLUSION

A medicated cigarette is an interesting concept to learn and explore.

It is a concept originated from ancient traditional system of medicine. This concept is not that much popular and explored in modern system of medicine. Although researches going on in this field but there are still plenty of scope for many unexplored drugs/therapies.

This unusual dosage form could also be used for the delivery of drugs to the particular site and for the curing of diseases.

This concept of drug delivery could be used for targeting drug by the delivering the medicinal actives to the particular site of “naso-brain gateway”.

The herbal/medicated cigarettes are beneficial for quit smoking but less harmful to the human beings.

This system of drug delivery could be an efficacious and patient friendly.

Systemic research and proper data collection interpretation could give a scientific rationale to the traditional claims. That could serve a bridge between traditional and modern system of medicine.

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